

The conservation status of terrestrial molluscs on the Caribbean Netherlands: a baseline assessment for Bonaire, Saba, and Sint Eustatius

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The terrestrial mollusc fauna of the Caribbean Netherlands, comprising the islands of Bonaire, Saba, and Sint Eustatius (collectively known as the BES islands), represents a distinctive and vulnerable component of regional biodiversity. Characterized by high rates of island endemics and species with a restricted distribution, this fauna is increasingly threatened by habitat loss and degradation, due to the growing population and urbanization, overgrazing by goats and the effects of hurricanes (that might occur more frequently due to climate change). Another serious risk is predation and competition for food and space by exotic species (in particular the recently introduced New Guinea flatworm) and limited policy measures to prevent the import of new exotic species. An overview is given on the current state of knowledge concerning the distribution, taxonomy, abundance, ecological preferences, and conservation threats facing terrestrial molluscs on the BES islands. Our findings underscore the urgent need for comprehensive monitoring, improved taxonomic resolution, and effective management strategies to mitigate current and emerging threats.

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INTRODUCTION

Island ecosystems are globally recognized for their unique biodiversity, particularly for taxa such as terrestrial molluscs

that exhibit high levels of endemism due to geographic isolation and low dispersal capabilities. However, insular land snails are also among the most threatened animals on earth, already having suffered extensive human-caused extinctions. Extinctions of land snails represent the majority of currently known extinctions among all plants and animals (Lydeard et al, 2004; IUCN, 2020), and more than 70% of these took place on oceanic islands (Régnier, Fontaine & Bouchet, 2009). The Caribbean Islands Biodiversity Hotspot is one of 36 biodiversity hotspots in the world. Biodiversity hotspots hold at least 1,500 plant species found nowhere else and have lost at least 70 percent of their original habitat extent (Mittermeier et al., 2004; Caribbean Natural Resources Institute, 2019). So the Caribbean region is no exception, and within it, the BES islands serve as a microcosm of these patterns.

Since the constitutional restructuring of the Kingdom of the Netherlands in 2010, the Caribbean islands of Bonaire, Saba, and St. Eustatius have formally become part of the Netherlands. The Netherlands Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Food Security and Nature has taken on the ultimate responsibility for the implementation and enforcement of seven international nature conservation treaties for the islands. For the evaluation of the nature policy and the drafting of new nature policy plans, every 5 or 6 years a report on the state of nature is made.

Despite the ecological importance and vulnerability of terrestrial molluscs, they remain, just like other invertebrate groups, one of the least studied and most underprotected faunal groups in the region. More attention for this species group in nature conservation policy is urgently needed. Fortunately, the State of Nature report 2025 (Debrot et al., 2025) was the first report that gave special attention to the conservation state of terrestrial molluscs (van Leeuwen & Neckheim, 2025).

In this article, the first comprehensive assessment of the conservation status of terrestrial molluscs on the BES islands is presented, drawing on recent fieldwork, literature reviews, and expert assessments to establish a baseline for future monitoring and conservation efforts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data were compiled from multiple sources, including a comprehensive field survey conducted in 2023 on Bonaire, historic records from the 20th century, and recent incidental observations on Saba and St. Eustatius. Species presence, abundance, and habitat preferences were recorded across over 300 localities on Bonaire. For Saba and St. Eustatius, abundance data are largely inferred from past records and limited recent sampling. Species were categorized based on distribution (island endemic, regional endemic, indigenous, or exotic), and conservation status was inferred from IUCN criteria where applicable.

RESULTS

Species richness

Table 2 gives an overview of all terrestrial mollusc species reported from the BES islands.

On Bonaire an extensive inventory of terrestrial molluscs was made in 2023 (van Leeuwen, Bakker & Neckheim, 2025). This survey established distribution baselines for most species. For Saba and Sint Eustatius a comparable baseline study is not published yet. So the available knowledge is based on older publications and publications based on a limited amount of fieldwork.

For Saba Table 2 is based on Haas, 1960; Haas, 1962; Clench, 1970; van Leeuwen, Boeken & Hovestadt, 2015 and Neckheim, 2021. For St. Eustatius Table 2 is based on Haas 1960 and 1962; Hovestadt, 1980; van der Valk, 1987; van Leeuwen & Hewitt, 2016; and for *Lissachatina fulica* personal observations of the author in February, 2025.

A total of 57 terrestrial mollusc species are currently recognized from the BES islands: 31 on Bonaire, 28 on Saba, and 23 on St. Eustatius. Bonaire hosts the highest number of island endemics (eight), including the uniquely localized *Cerion uva bonairensis* and the genus *Bonairea*. Saba has no known island endemics but includes six taxa endemic to the Lesser Antilles. St. Eustatius harbors one island endemic (*Lapa quillensis*) and three regionally restricted taxa. These findings demonstrate the ecological uniqueness of each island's mollusc fauna.

To categorise the abundance of each species on Bonaire the database of the Bonaire Estafette Expedition 2023 was used. This database contains 974 records and forms a good baseline. A comparable baseline study was not available for Saba and Sint Eustatius. For this reason I created a database of all observations of terrestrial molluscs per island available to me, resulting in a database with 312 records for Saba and 243 records for St. Eustatius. The abundance categories per island depend on the relative number of observation of each species per island as shown in Table 1.

	Number of records		
	Bonaire	Saba	St. Eustatius
Rare	1-10	1-4	1-4
Uncommon	11-40	5-14	5-12
Common	41-100	15-40	13-35
Abundant	>100	>40	>35
total number of records in the database	974	312	243

Table 1. Abundance categories per island, used in Table 2.

The species lists seem to be incomplete yet, and more species might be expected for both islands when an actual overview will be made, based on more and actual fieldwork. Typical of this is that Neckheim (2021) found 2 new species for Saba during 1 day of field work. On the other hand, some of the species from Saba have not been reported from the island for over half of a century, but due to the limited amount of fieldwork done on this island, we are not able to conclude if these species disappeared or still live there.

Taxonomic and ecological classification

Species were categorized into four main distribution groups:

- 1 Island endemics: taxa restricted to a single island or its satellite (e.g., *Tudora aurantia wassauensis*).
- 2 Regionally endemic taxa: occurring on a small number of islands, situated close to each other's (e.g., *Amphibulima patula*).
- 3 Indigenous species: taxa that occur in a wider area in the Caribbean and/or American region and/or parts of Central/South America (e.g., *Mesembrinus elongatus*).
- 4 Exotic species: taxa from outside the Caribbean region which are likely to be introduced by human activity (e.g., *Lissachatina fulica*).

Fig. 1 shows the species composition for each island according to these categories.

Endemic taxa deserve special attention in strategies to protect the biodiversity of the islands. An analysis of the IUCN Red List worldwide has shown that land molluscs are the species group with the highest number of documented extinctions (Lydeard et al., 2004). And within this group, island endemics are the most vulnerable (Fernández-Palacios et al., 2021). This makes that land molluscs of the Dutch Antillean islands are a very important species group to consider when developing policy and management plans to protect the biodiversity of the islands.

Terrestrial molluscs of the BES islands are not included in any list of protected species, for example from the national or island government. None of the terrestrial mollusc species of these islands have been assessed for the IUCN Global

Family	Name	Abundance Bonaire	Abundance Saba	Abundance St Eustatius	Habitat	Status
Achatinidae	<i>Allopeas gracile</i> (T. Hutton, 1834)	R	R	U	H, L	Exotic
Achatinidae	<i>Allopeas micra</i> (A. d'Orbigny, 1835)	R	U	C	C,L,F	Indigenous
Achatinidae	<i>Beckianum beckianum</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)		C	C	L, F	Indigenous
Achatinidae	<i>Cryptelasmus canteroiana cienfuegosensis</i> Pilsbry, 1906		R		H	Exotic
Achatinidae	<i>Lissachatina fulica</i> (Bowdich, 1822)	R		A	H	Exotic
Achatinidae	<i>Neosubulina harterti</i> E. A. Smith, 1898 •	U			C	Endemic Bonaire
Achatinidae	<i>Obeliscus plicatellum</i> (Guppy, 1868)		R		L	Endemic Lesser Antilles
Achatinidae	<i>Obeliscus swiftianus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1852)			R	L, F	Indigenous
Achatinidae	<i>Opeas hannense</i> (Rang, 1831)		U	U	L, F	Exotic
Achatinidae	<i>Paropeas achatinaceum</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)	U			H	Exotic
Achatinidae	<i>Subulina octona</i> (Bruguière, 1789)	R	A	A	H,L,F	Exotic
Amphibulimidae	<i>Amphibulima patula</i> (Bruguière, 1789)		R		F	Endemic Lesser Antilles
Annulariidae	<i>Bonairea maculata</i> (H. B. Baker, 1924) •	U			C	Endemic Bonaire
Annulariidae	<i>Tudora aurantia aurantia</i> (Wood, 1828) •	C			C, L	Endemic Bonaire
Annulariidae	<i>Tudora aurantia wassauensis</i> H. B. Baker, 1924 •	A			C, L	Endemic Bonaire
Bulimulidae	<i>Bulimulus fraterculus fraterculus</i> (Potiez & Michaud, 1838) •		U	C	L, F	Endemic Lesser Antilles
Bulimulidae	<i>Bulimulus guadalupensis</i> (Bruguière, 1789)		C	U	H,L,F	Indigenous
Bulimulidae	<i>Bulimulus lehmanni</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1865)		R		F	Endemic Lesser Antilles
Bulimulidae	<i>Mesembrinus elongatus</i> (Röding, 1789)	C		U	L, F	Indigenous
Cerionidae	<i>Cerion uva bonairensis</i> H. B. Baker, 1924 •	A			C, L	Endemic Bonaire
Euconulidae	<i>Guppya gundlachii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1840)		R	R	F	Indigenous
Ferussaciidae	<i>Karolus consobrinus</i> (A. d'Orbigny, 1841)	R	U	R	C,L,F	Indigenous
Gastrocoptidae	<i>Gastrocopta barbadensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)		R	C	C,L,F	Indigenous
Gastrocoptidae	<i>Gastrocopta curacoana</i> Pilsbry, 1924	U			C, F	Indigenous
Gastrocoptidae	<i>Gastrocopta octonaria</i> Pilsbry, 1924	U			C, F	Indigenous
Gastrocoptidae	<i>Gastrocopta polyptyx</i> Pilsbry, 1916		R		L	Indigenous
Gastrocoptidae	<i>Gastrocopta servilis riisei</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1852)	R	R		C, F	Indigenous
Gastrocoptidae	<i>Gastrocopta servilis servilis</i> (A. A. Gould, 1843)			U	L	Indigenous
Gastrodontidae	<i>Zonitoides arboreus</i> (Say, 1817)		R	R	F	Indigenous
Helicinidae	<i>Helicina fasciata</i> Lamarck, 1822 •		A	C	L,H,F	Endemic Lesser Antilles
Helicinidae	<i>Lucidella lirata</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1847)	R			F	Indigenous
Helicinidae	<i>Lucidella striatula</i> (A. Férussac, 1827)			R	L,F	Indigenous
Helicinidae	<i>Stoastomops walkeri</i> H. B. Baker, 1924 •	U			C	Endemic Bonaire
Oleacinidae	<i>Melaniella gracillima sanctithomensis</i> (Pilsbry, 1907)		R		L	Endemic Lesser Antilles
Oxychilidae	<i>Lapa quillensis</i> (de Winter, van Leeuwen & Hovestadt, 2016) •			U	F	Endemic St Eustatius
Polygyridae	<i>Polygyra cereolus</i> (Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1818)	R			H	Exotic
Polygyridae	<i>Praticolella griseola</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1841)	R			H	Exotic
Pristilomatidae	<i>Hawaiiia minuscula</i> (A. Binney, 1841)	R			C, F	Exotic ?
Pupillidae	<i>Pupoides nitidulus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1839)	C		R	C,L,F	Indigenous

Continued on next page

Family	Name	Abundance Bonaire	Abundance Saba	Abundance St Eustatius	Habitat	Status
Sagdidae	<i>Hojeda</i> spec.			R	L, F	Indigenous?
Sagdidae	<i>Hyalosagda subaquila</i> (Shuttleworth, 1854) •			U	L	Endemic Lesser Antilles
Sagdidae	<i>Lacteoluna selenina</i> (A. A. Gould, 1848)		R		F	Indigenous
Sagdidae	<i>Setidiscus crinitus</i> (Fulton, 1917)	R			C, F	Indigenous
Scolodontidae	<i>Happia</i> spec.		R		F	Indigenous?
Streptaxidae	<i>Gulella bicolor</i> (T. Hutton, 1834)	R			C, H, F	Exotic
Streptaxidae	<i>Streptartemon glaber</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1850)	R	C		H, F	Indigenous, exotic on Bonaire
Streptaxidae	<i>Tomostele musaecola</i> (Morelet, 1860)		U		H, L	Exotic
Succineidae	<i>Succinea concordialis</i> A. A. Gould, 1848	R			H	Exotic
Succineidae	<i>Succinea gyrata</i> Gibbons, 1879 •	A			C, L	Endemic Bonaire + Curaçao
Succineidae	<i>Succinea riisei</i> L. Pfeiffer, 1853		R		L	Indigenous
Urocoptidae	<i>Brachypodella gibbonsi</i> Baker, 1924 •	U			C	Endemic Bonaire
Urocoptidae	<i>Microceramus bonairensis bonairensis</i> (E. A. Smith, 1898) •	C			C	Endemic Bonaire
Urocoptidae	<i>Pseudopineria viequensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1856)		R		H	Indigenous
Valloniidae	<i>Pupisoma dioscoricola</i> (C. B. Adams, 1845)	R		R	L, F	Indigenous
Valloniidae	<i>Pupisoma macneilli</i> (G. H. Clapp, 1918)		R	R	L, F	Indigenous
Veronicellidae	Veronicellidae indet.	R	R		H, F	Exotic
Zachrysiidae	<i>Zachrysia provisoria</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1858)	R	C		H, L	Exotic
	Total number of taxa	31	28	23	57	

Table 2. Known status of land mollusc species and subspecies for Bonaire, St. Eustatius and Saba, Netherlands Caribbean as based on listed publications. Abundance: R = rare, U = uncommon, C = common, A = abundant. See Table 1 for abundance categories per island. Habitat: C = calcareous rocks, L = lowlands, F = forest/ rainforest, H = human environment like villages, gardens and farmland. Taxa marked with a bullet point (•) are figured in this paper. Sources: Haas, 1960; Haas, 1962; Clench, 1970; Breure, 1974; Hovestadt, 1980; van der Valk, 1987; van Leeuwen et al., 2015; van Leeuwen & Hewitt, 2016; de Winter et al., 2016; Hovestadt & van Leeuwen, 2017; Neckheim, 2021, van Leeuwen et al., 2023; van Leeuwen et al., 2025.

Fig. 1. Species composition of the BES islands, grouped by the distribution range of the species. ■ island endemic; ■ range restricted; ■ Indigenous; ■ exotic.

Red List (IUCN, 2024). So practically nothing has been known about the status of this important and vulnerable component of the native biodiversity of the Dutch Caribbean.

Monographs on the terrestrial mollusc fauna of other Caribbean islands are scarce. Examples of the last century are Puerto Rico (van der Schalie, 1948), Guadeloupe (Bouchet & Pointier, 1998), Dominica (Robinson et al., 2009), Martinique (Delannoye et al., 2015), St. Kitts and Nevis (Breure et al., 2016), the ABC islands (Hovestadt & van Leeuwen, 2017), and St. Martin (Hovestadt & Neckheim, 2020, with additions in Neckheim, 2021 and in Neckheim & Hovestadt, 2021). These studies show that the occurrence of island endemics and taxa with a very limited distribution is characteristic for many Caribbean islands, as is the case to islands worldwide (Solem, 1984; Proios, Cameron & Triantis, 2021). Distribution data in GBIF (2024) show the same.

Several taxa of terrestrial molluscs of the BES islands are limited to one island or only some Caribbean islands. The category of indigenous species refers to species that are spread over a larger group of Caribbean islands, and some of them also occur on the mainland of Venezuela, Central America or Florida (GBIF, 2024). This underpins the big importance of the terrestrial mollusc fauna of the BES islands within the Caribbean.

Species composition and distribution: the islands compared

There is a major difference in the land mollusc fauna composition between Bonaire on the one hand, and Saba and St. Eustatius on the other (Table 2). There is relatively little overlap in species, and the overlapping species are all exotic species or species with a wide distribution in the Caribbean region. This can be attributed to the large distance between Bonaire, situated in the southern part of the Caribbean Sea, and Saba and St. Eustatius situated in the northern part of the Lesser Antilles. Other reasons are the differences in geology and climate. Bonaire has an arid climate, an abundance of limestone habitat next to volcanic rocks and a low maximum altitude. Saba and St. Eustatius are volcanic islands with consequently mainly volcanic soils, much higher maximum altitudes and higher humidity.

The overlap in terrestrial mollusc fauna between Saba and St. Eustatius is large, with about half of the taxa being found on both islands, including two species that are endemic to the Lesser Antilles.

Although Bonaire is much closer to the mainland of South America than Saba and St. Eustatius, Bonaire has by far the highest number and proportion of island endemics and range restricted taxa (Fig. 1).

While Bonaire has the largest number of island endemics, Saba and St. Eustatius have the highest species richness per unit of surface area (Table 3). This is remarkable, especially

when one considers the likelihood that even more species occur on these islands than are currently known. Bonaire is much larger in surface area, but the island is much flatter, so it has fewer different “climatic” microhabitats than Saba and St. Eustatius. The fact that the Bonaire fauna has many more endemics can be explained by the much higher age of Bonaire compared to Saba and St. Eustatius, which are fairly recent volcanoes from the Tertiary, while Bonaire was formed in the much older Miocene.

	Bonaire	Saba	St. Eustatius
Surface in km ²	288	13	21
Highest peak in metres	240	887	601
Number of terrestrial mollusc species	31	28	23
Number of terrestrial mollusc species/km ²	0.1	2.2	1.1

Table 3. Surface area, altitude and total number of species known of each island. Source: Wikipedia, 2024.

Population size on the BES islands

There should be little local concern at present for the common and abundant mollusc species. This is also the case for some endemic taxa: on Bonaire the endemic *Cerion uva bonairensis*, *Tudora aurantia aurantia* and *Tudora aurantia wassauensis* have healthy populations. The endemic and colourful *Helicina fasciata* is abundant on Saba. This species is much less abundant on St. Eustatius, but the population seems to be viable there too (however it became highly endangered on St. Martin).

On Bonaire four endemic taxa are uncommon, which means they have a limited distribution, and they occur in low numbers. Uncommon island endemics on Bonaire are *Neosubulina harterti*, *Bonairea maculata*, *Stoastomops walkeri* and *Brachypodella gibbonsi*.

On Saba and St. Eustatius, the abundancy in Table 2 is a rough estimation only, due to the much scarcer data available about the current distribution. The only island endemic of St. Eustatius, *Lapa quillensis*, is uncommon. It lives in low numbers in a very limited area. On Saba five such endemic species are rare or uncommon: *Obeliscus plicatellum*, *Amphibulima patula*, *Bulimulus fraterculus fraterculus*, *Bulimulus lehmanni*, and *Melaniella gracillima sanctithomensis*. On Saba, *Amphibulima patula* seems to be restricted to the higher parts of Mount Scenery and the elfin forest. On St. Eustatius *Hyalosagda subaquila* is uncommon. This species is endemic to the Lesser Antilles.

Moreover, 8 indigenous species are rare or uncommon on Bonaire, 11 on Saba and 11 on St. Eustatius. Some of these spe-

Figs 2-14. Endemic terrestrial molluscs occurring on Bonaire, Saba and Sint Eustatius. **2.** *Cerion uva bonairensis*, 24 mm, Bonaire. **3.** *Tudora aurantia wassauensis*, 16.6 mm, Bonaire. **4.** *Tudora aurantia aurantia*, 18.5 mm, Bonaire. **5.** *Neosubulina harterti*, 7.5 mm, Bonaire. **6.** *Bulimulus fraterculus fraterculus*, 15.3 mm, Saba. **7.** *Microceramus bonairensis bonairensis*, 6.8 mm, Bonaire. **8.** *Brachypodella gibbonsi*, 7.2 mm, Bonaire. **9.** *Bonairea maculata*, 8.0 mm, Bonaire. **10.** *Succinea gyrata*, 12 mm, Bonaire. **11.** *Stoastomops walkeri*, 2.5 mm, Bonaire. **12.** *Hyalosagda subaquila*, 4.7 mm, St. Eustatius. **13.** *Helicina fasciata*, 8.0 mm, Saba. **14.** *Helicina fasciata*, 9.4 mm, Saba. Photos 7, 8, 9 and 11: Hannco Bakker; other photos Sylvia van Leeuwen.

cies occur on two or three of the BES islands. The following indigenous species are uncommon or rare on all BES islands where they occur: *Obeliscus swiftianus*, *Guppya gundlachii*, *Karolus consobrinus*, *Gastrocopta curacoana*, *Gastrocopta octonaria*, *Gastrocopta polyptyx*, *Gastrocopta servilis riisei*, *Gastrocopta servilis servilis*, *Zonitoides arboreus*, *Lucidella lirata*, *Lucidella striatula*, *Setidiscus crinitus*, *Succinea riisei*, *Pseudopineria viequensis*, *Pupisoma dioscoricola* and *Pupisoma macneilli*. These taxa might have small and vulnerable populations although some taxa are very small and might have been overlooked on Saba and/or St. Eustatius.

Some rare species from Saba (Table 2) have been found most recently more than 50 years ago. For these species, it is unsure if they still survive on the island or if they have disappeared. This is the case for *Cryptelasmus canteroiana cienfuegosensis*, *Gastrocopta polyptyx*, *Gastrocopta servilis riisei*, *Pseudopineria viequensis*, and *Succinea riisei*. However, the Conservation State of the regionally more-widespread indigenous species remains totally unknown due to the lack of quantitative assessments of terrestrial molluscs in the Caribbean region.

HABITAT PREFERENCES AND ECOLOGICAL ROLE

Terrestrial molluscs are relatively immobile species that have limited possibilities to react to sudden changes in their habitat or to move to another more suitable habitat. For this reason, the presence of terrestrial molluscs is a good indicator for the quality of nature in a certain area. Due to a lack of studies, very little is known about the species-specific ecology of most Antillean species. This is not only the case in the Caribbean Netherlands but in the Caribbean as a whole.

In Table 2, four main mollusc habitats are distinguished: calcareous rocks, lowlands, forest/ rainforest and the human environment, based on the localities where the molluscs were observed. This Table shows that each habitat has its own species composition. On Bonaire, mollusc diversity is highest in calcareous rock habitats, especially karst formations and limestone cliffs, which provide essential calcium carbonate and stable microclimates. These areas host nearly all endemic and indigenous species. Nearly half of the endemics of Bonaire are limited to these limestone areas only. Molluscs are vulnerable to dehydration, so most of them live hidden under stones, in holes and cracks and on places shadowed by trees and shrubs. For the same reason also, north-faced calcareous cliffs can be relatively rich in molluscs. The most important area for endemic molluscs on Bonaire is the Karst and Cave Reserve. The endemic taxa *Cerion uva bonairensis*, *Tudora aurantia aurantia* and *Tudora aurantia wassauensis* do also live in limestone areas,

but in lower numbers they also occur in volcanic areas. These habitat preferences can not only be seen at the level of individual taxa, sister taxa of the same genus on Curaçao and Aruba have the same habitat preferences (Hovestadt & van Leeuwen, 2017). The same is valid for St Martin, where the calcareous parts of the island are the most rich areas for terrestrial snails.

Snails of the family Succineidae are extremely vulnerable for dehydration. They are land molluscs, but they only live in the vicinity of water or moist places.

In contrast, on Saba and St. Eustatius calcareous soils are absent or very sparse, due to the volcanic nature of the islands. An exception is the White Wall on St. Eustatius at the southern flanks of the Quill volcano. It consists partly of uplifted shallow-water limestone deposits from coral reefs mixed with material ejected from the volcano (ash, cinders). However the number of molluscs on the White Wall is not much higher than on other parts of the Quill. On these islands the lowlands with natural vegetation and the forest/ rainforest are the most important habitats for endemic and indigenous mollusc species.

Many taxa from lowlands and from forests/rain forests live in the leaf litter layer or under dead wood and areas shadowed by the undergrowth of shrubs, where they are well-protected against dehydration. Some species live on the trunks, branches and leaves of trees and shrubs. The indigenous *Mesembrinus elongatus* is arboreal and lives on a limited number of plant species (Van Buurt, 2016). Also *Helicina fasciata*, endemic species of the Lesser Antilles, is an arboreal species with preferences for particular plants (personal observation of the author but not studied systematically yet).

What the land mollusc taxa of the BES islands exactly eat is poorly studied for most species, and the way they feed is just globally derived from family characteristics for most species. In general, it is known that many of them eat detritus, algae, fungi or dead plant material, and thus contribute to the composting of the soil. Other species live on trees, shrubs and herbal plants where they scrape algae or lichens from the plants without causing damage to the plants. Some taxa are plant eaters that eat from the plant stems and leaves, while others are predators or scavengers. For example, snails of the family Scolodontidae are grazers and/or predators on mobile prey and also Streptaxidae feed on mobile prey (Molluscabase, 2024).

In turn, the land snails provide a valuable food source for insects (especially ground beetles), centipedes, frogs and birds, and maybe also other reptiles may eat snails. The empty shells of molluscs provide shelter for bees and spiders to hide in or to build their nests. Even the shells of terrestrial snails are used as shelter by the Caribbean Land Hermit crab (*Coenobita clypeatus*).

The biology and life cycle of most taxa of the BES islands

Figs 15-21. Endemic terrestrial molluscs occurring on Bonaire, Saba and Sint Eustatius. **15.** *Lapa quillensis*, 5.2 mm, St. Eustatius (holotype, collection Naturalis Biodiversity Center). **16.** *Amphibulima patula*, live animal, Saba. **17.** *Tudora aurantia wassauensis*, live animal, Bonaire. **18.** *Helicina fasciata*, live animal, Saba. **19.** *Cerion uva bonairensis*, live animals, Bonaire. **20.** *Helicina fasciata*, live animal, St. Eustatius. **21.** *Bulimulus fraterculus*, live animal, St. Eustatius. Photos of live specimens taken in situ. Photo 15: Ton de Winter; photo 17: Michiel Boeken; other photos: Sylvia van Leeuwen.

is not exactly known but only derived from the general family level. Many terrestrial molluscs are hermaphrodites, which means that they possess both male and female reproductive organs and may be capable of self-fertilization. But for example, *Tudora*'s are of separate sex (males being much smaller than females).

More is known about the food preferences and biology of species that are harmful to agriculture or human health, and invasive species. For example, more detailed studies have been done on the Giant African snail *Lissachatina fulica*, several species of the slug family Veronicellidae and the Cuban garden snail *Zachysia provisoria*. The results, including plant species and other things they prefer to eat and their reproduction, are summarized in factsheets in the Cabi Compendium (Cabi, 2018).

THREATS TO CONSERVATION

Availability of knowledge

A basic requirement for the assessment of the mollusc fauna of an island is that it is known which species live on each island, how they need to be named and how they are related to similar taxa from other islands. Secondly: knowledge about their habitat preference and distribution over the islands. Thirdly, a reference point in the past is needed to get a better insight in development of the mollusc faunas: which species disappeared or were newly established on the islands, which species are declining or increasing.

For Bonaire a baseline, including species composition, distribution and habitat preferences, was created for the first time in 2023. For Saba and St. Eustatius no baseline has yet been made. It is highly advisable to create these in the near future. Also the taxonomy of the mollusc species of the BES islands is not always clear.

There is no systematic monitoring system for molluscs of the BES islands and the available data are insufficient to calculate trends. For all three islands a quantitative reference point in the past is lacking. Perhaps (but not for sure) the material that Wagenaar Hummelink collected and that is stored in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, will allow to create a kind of reference point in the past. This requires that the material will be identified, digitalised, analysed and published.

Threats to mollusc conservation

Three factors are identified that are of may become a threat to native terrestrial molluscs in the Dutch Caribbean: invasive species, habitat degradation and a lack of legal protection. These will be explained further.

Invasive species

Due to the growing amount of transport of people and

goods the number of exotic mollusc species is growing. Exotic species can compete with indigenous species for food and space. Some exotic species will live an unobtrusive life, others can be harmful to indigenous molluscs, or even to agriculture and human health. The growing number of exotic species was clearly visible on Bonaire (van Leeuwen et al., 2023; de Waart, van Leeuwen & Kmentova, 2025) and it is likely that this is also happening on Saba and St. Eustatius. Shortly after their introduction, the distribution of exotic species will mainly be limited to the human environment, but this may change over time. Several exotic species became well established. For example, the introduced species *Subulina octona* has become very widely distributed over St. Eustatius and Saba (personal observations of author), where it was even found in natural areas like the crater bottom of the Quill and the top of Mount Scenery.

The African Giant Snail (*Lissachatina fulica*) poses threats to agriculture, native molluscs, and human health as a vector for pathogens like *Angiostrongylus cantonensis*. Trials on St. Eustatius showed that it seems feasible to control or even eradicate the African Giant snail using a combination of snail baits and handpicking, combined with dedicated monitoring (Debrot et al., 2016, 2017). However, these methods need to be applied consistently and during a very long period to eradicate this species completely. Notwithstanding these efforts the species is still present on St. Eustatius. The eradication measures taken on St. Eustatius were not strong enough and depended too much on the voluntary co-operation of inhabitants. Due to this, the situation has since grown out of hand. By early 2025, the species was abundant on the island and had spread across almost the entire built-up area. The species even approached the edge of the Quill National Park (personal observations, February 2025). Because the Giant African snail eats a lot of plants, this could have a negative effect on the shrub and herb layer in the park, which is important part of the habitat of terrestrial snails. It also appears that the residents of Sint Eustatius were not well informed about the health risks (personal observations of author, February 2025). *Lissachatina fulica* recently entered Bonaire and when strong eradication measures are not taken soon, the species can also become a problem on Bonaire. A factsheet that can be used to develop measures is available (van Leeuwen, 2023).

Another invasive species that poses a threat to terrestrial snails is the New Guinea flatworm (*Platydemus manokwari*), a known mollusc predator. It was discovered on Bonaire in 2023 (de Waart & van Leeuwen, 2024a, 2024b) and has also been reported from Saba and St. Martin (de Waart, van Leeuwen & Kmentova, 2025). The New Guinea flatworm is ranked in the IUCN top 100 most invasive alien species in the world because it is an effective predator that poses a serious threat to native snails (Global Invasive Species Database 2010). On some Pacific islands this flatworm

Figs 22-27. Habitats for land molluscs on Bonaire, Saba and Sint Eustatius. **22.** Saba, Mount Scenery seen from Windwardside. **23.** Saba, elfin forest on the top of Mount Scenery. **24.** Bonaire, limestone platform with natural vegetation in the Karst and Cave Reserve. **25.** St. Eustatius, The Quill seen from Boven National Park. **26.** St. Eustatius, dry tropical forest in Boven National Park. **27.** St. Eustatius, tropical rainforest and large rocks in the crater of The Quill. Photos: Sylvia van Leeuwen.

was an important factor in the extinction of several indigenous mollusc species (Sugiura & Yamaura, 2009). Some years ago, this species also appeared in Florida, and now the populations of endemic tree snails are declining rapidly (Lopez et al., 2022; personal observations by Johan van Berck and Steve Rosenthal). These tree snails are most similar in size and behaviour to the indigenous *Mesembrinus elongatus* and also the island endemic *Cerion uva bonaiensis*, and have approximately the same size. However, the flatworm also preys on much smaller species like *Zonitoides arboreus* and Clausiliidae (Kaneda, Kitagawa & Ichinohe, 1990). On Bonaire and Curaçao the flatworms were found in garden centres, and that makes it plausible that the worms came with imported potted plants. Many imported plants on the Dutch Caribbean islands come from Florida. The New Guinea flatworm is not only a risk for molluscs, but also for human health. The flatworm can be the host of the Rat lungworm, a nematode that can cause meningitis in humans (Thunnissen et al., 2020). What the effect of the flatworm will be on the mollusc populations on the BES islands, is yet unknown. However, given from what can be learned from its effects elsewhere, a “wait and see” approach is not advisable. If still feasible, full eradication should be strived for and tools need to be developed with which to combat and control this new threat.

Habitat degradation

Key threats include urban expansion, a lower vegetation cover in forests, due to overgrazing by introduced herbivores (goats, donkeys), and increased hurricane activity. These factors degrade the moist, sheltered microhabitats that molluscs rely on, particularly in forests and limestone areas. Cutting trees in an arid environment also has effects on all the small animals, not only snails, that have lived under that tree.

On Bonaire the vegetation was highly affected by the grazing of goats and donkeys (de Freitas et al., 2005). On Saba and St. Eustatius the vegetation is also affected by grazers and moreover the forests, especially the very humid elfin forests, were negatively affected by the hurricanes in 2017 (de Freitas et al., 2014; de Freitas et al., 2016; van Andel et al., 2016; Eppinga & Pucko, 2018; Jansen, 2020; Van Proosdij, in prep.). The freely roaming goats mainly eat from the plants and young trees in the undergrowth, and they also eat dead leaves. Consequently, a drier microclimate is created on and in the soil. Most land snails are highly dependent on a moist, undisturbed microclimate and they are very sensitive to dehydration. On Saba effective measures resulted in a significant decline of the goat population in nature areas, but on St. Eustatius and Bonaire they are still very numerous.

Urban expansion is also a factor leading to a decline of suitable habitats. The population on Bonaire grew quickly: from 15,700 in 2011 to 26,600 in 2025. The CBS expects that

the population of Bonaire will increase further to 34,200 in 2035. The population size of Saba and Sint Eustatius is relatively stable and CBS does not expect large changes until 2035 (CBS, 2024). However on Sint Eustatius large parts of the ‘Cultuurvlakte’ already became urbanised and on all three islands, there are several construction projects that will take up space from natural habitats. On St. Martin at least three terrestrial molluscs species became highly endangered due to habitat loss (van Bussel, 2022).

Lack of legal protection

Despite their ecological importance, no terrestrial mollusc species from the BES islands are currently protected under any international, national or local legislation.

On Bonaire, a big risk is that the most important habitats for endemic molluscs, calcareous rocks, forested limestone platforms and limestone cliffs, are mainly situated outside the Washington Slagbaai National Park. The Bonaire Cave and Karst Reserve is among the richest mollusc areas, both in number of species and in population size (number of individuals). The name suggests an area that is protected, but in fact only the interior caves are protected, not the coral platform with indigenous trees above and surrounding the caves that is so important for the molluscs. The risk of this poor protection is that there is no legal basis to act against plans that may contribute to the decline or even extinction of endemic species. The Research Agenda in the ‘Management plan 2022-2028’ for the Slagbaai National Park on Bonaire gives special attention to molluscs and other invertebrates. The management goal is to develop basic data on diversity of insects and molluscs in the park (which endemic species are found in the park and are of conservation concern and which invasive species are found in the park that are invasive and potential harmful) (Crestian et al., 2022).

On Saba and St. Eustatius, the most important mollusc areas are within the Saba National Land Park (which has been part of the Mount Scenery National Park since 2018) and the Quill and Boven National Parks, which have a protected status and are managed by nature management organisations. This gives a basic protection to the habitats of the molluscs. In the management plans for the parks on Saba (MacRae & De Meyer, 2018) and St. Eustatius (Esteban, MacRae & Blok, 2009) there are no specific measures to protect endemic terrestrial molluscs, but molluscs will benefit from general management measures, for example to manage free-roaming livestock. On Saba good progress is made to remove free roaming goats from the national park (personal observation, January 2025). However, on Sint Eustatius this proves to be more difficult to achieve. The number of free-roaming goats is still very high on that island (personal observation February 2025).

The general threat of invasive species is recognised in all

management plans. However, there is no special attention for the harmful New Guinea flatworm *Platydemus manokwari* and other species of landflatworms that might be predators on molluscs, because these species were unknown to occur at the time the management plans were written. It also requires more research to develop effective measures to deal with these species (Debrot et al., 2025).

CONSERVATION STATUS

The “Conservation State” of the terrestrial molluscs of the BES-islands was assessed by van Leeuwen & Neckheim (2025) according to the methods prescribed by European Union’s Habitats Directive (HD). This includes the assessment of distribution, population size, habitat and future prospects. These aspects are already explained above. Their assessment is summarized in Table 4.

Aspect terrestrial molluscs	2024
Distribution	Unfavourable-bad
Population	Unfavourable-bad
Habitat	Favourable
Future prospects	Unfavourable-bad
Overall Assessment of Conservation State	Unfavourable-bad

Table 4. Diagnostic scores for the four different State of Nature criteria for the terrestrial molluscs of the Caribbean Netherlands as well as an overall Caribbean Netherlands conservation assessment for the year 2024.

Although not studied and described systematically, the impression is that the situation on the other Dutch Caribbean islands, Aruba, Curaçao and St. Maarten is similar. Limestone areas on these islands harbour endemic species that are currently unprotected, and without conservation measures these species are at risk too.

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The terrestrial molluscs of the Caribbean Netherlands represent a unique and fragile component of Caribbean biodiversity. Their conservation status is currently unfavourable due to invasive species, habitat degradation, limited legal protection, and lack of systematic data. Immediate action – including expanded protection, targeted monitoring, and invasive species control – is essential to preserve these irreplaceable faunal communities. The implementation of the recommended management and research priorities will be critical in halting further biodiversity loss on these ecologically valuable islands.

To address the pressing conservation challenges, three national conservation objectives were defined for the national government:

- 1 Increase local awareness about the uniqueness of the local mollusc fauna that includes many unique endemic taxa. Be proud of them.
- 2 Protect the endemic mollusc species and their habitats to safeguard this unique and characteristic part of the biodiversity of the BES islands.
- 3 Locate the most important areas for endemic and indigenous molluscs on each island and prevent the habitats from becoming lost or deteriorated.

More specific van Leeuwen & Neckheim (2025) recommended the government to take the following measures:

- **Monitoring and taxonomic clarification:** Conduct a plan to fill the most important knowledge gaps for the terrestrial mollusc faunas. Give priority to a complete and actual inventory of the terrestrial mollusc faunas of Saba and St. Eustatius. Use molecular tools to resolve ambiguities in taxonomy among endemic taxa. Establish quantitative monitoring on all three islands.
- **Invasive Species Control:** Try to develop methods and a plan to eradicate or control the New Guinean flatworm *Platydemus manokwari*. Strengthen and renew measures to control the Giant African snail *Lissachatina fulica* on St. Eustatius, with special attention to the border zones of the Quill National Park. Develop a strict eradication plan for Bonaire, where the distribution of this snail is still limited. Monitor the effect of the measures. Also consider measures to prevent the import of more exotic species, especially with the import of potted plants. Also take measures to inform the inhabitants of St. Eustatius, Saba and Bonaire about the health risks of the Giant African snail and/or the New Guinea Flatworm and inform them how to act when they observe these species.
- **Habitat Protection:** Identify for each island the most important areas for endemic mollusc taxa. When these are situated outside the protected national parks, develop island land-use plans to safeguard sufficient mollusc habitat and vegetation in a natural state. Give priority to protect mollusc-rich limestone areas on Bonaire where the island endemics live, and the type localities of endemic taxa, because these are outside the national parks. For this reason, consider extending the protected area of the Bonaire Karst and Cave Reserve by including the upper part of the limestone terrace and the areas in between the caves in the protected zone. To improve the habitats, remove the free roaming goats from protected nature areas.
- **Public Engagement:** Educate local communities about molluscs’ ecological value, invasive species risks and the importance of protecting this vulnerable group of animals.

- Policy Integration: Include mollusc conservation in national and island-level biodiversity strategies.

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